

Integrating Traditional Chinese Medicine into Chronic Pain Care in Portugal: Neuroimmunological and Clinical Perspectives.

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Abstract

Chronic pain affects 42% of the Portuguese population, with a high socioeconomic impact. Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) offers promising therapies, such as acupuncture, electroacupuncture, herbal medicine, mind-body exercises (Tai Chi, *Qigong*), *Tui Na* massage, and moxibustion. This literature review aims to critically analyse the neurophysiological mechanisms and scientific evidence of these interventions in pain control. It concludes that these therapies modulate key neuroimmunological pathways. Acupuncture activates endogenous analgesia (β -endorphins) and suppresses inflammation via TLR2/NF- κ B. Phytotherapy blocks pain receptors and inhibits glial activation. *Qigong*, as a mind-body exercise, regulates the stress axis (cortisol). In addition, moxibustion improves circulation and reduces neuropathic pain. The integration of these approaches offers an effective multidimensional strategy, supported by current evidence, although standardized, randomized clinical trials with large samples from different populations are still needed.

Citation: Matos J.A., Relvas C., Silva M., Sebastião D. Integrating Traditional Chinese Medicine into Chronic Pain Care in Portugal: Neuroimmunological and Clinical Perspectives. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(3) 10.5281/zenodo.17257459

Keywords: Traditional Chinese Medicine; Pain Management; Acupuncture Mechanisms; Herbal Medicine; *Qigong*; Neuroimmunology; Chronic Pain.

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 15 September 2025

Reviewed: 28 September 2025

Revised: 2 October 2025

Accepted: 2 October 2025

Published: 3 October 2025

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1. Introduction

Chronic pain is a global public health problem, affecting more than 40% of the Portuguese population and generating significant socioeconomic costs ^{1,2}.

In Portugal, 70% of emergency cases are related to acute pain, whose poor management fosters chronification ^{3,4} while chronic pain affects more than 30% of adults, often associated with musculoskeletal disorders ⁵.

Chronic pain involves central sensitization and neuroimmunological dysregulation. Peripheral nociceptors activate ascending pathways to the cortex, triggering a process of persistent inflammation that lowers neuronal thresholds and amplifies pain perception. Effective control of this dysregulation requires strategies that act on these mechanisms, such as TCM therapies.

Pain is the most frequent symptom associated with disease, and it is the responsibility of healthcare professionals to identify its origin, relieve suffering, and restore functionality ⁶. According to the Portuguese Directorate-General of Health ⁷, acute pain is an important indicator of injury or physiological dysfunction and a common reason for seeking care. It represents a multifaceted sensory and emotional experience, resulting from injury, disease, or other medical conditions, whose treatment aims to improve quality of life and optimize daily performance ⁸.

Pain control should be a priority in healthcare, integrating the humanization of services. The transition from acute to chronic pain involves complex pathophysiological

mechanisms, including activation of peripheral nociceptors, transmission to the central nervous system, neuronal activation in the thalamus and cortex, and peripheral and central sensitization, all of which amplify pain perception⁹. The lowering of neuronal activation thresholds and the expansion of the sensitive area contribute to the chronification of pain.

TCM, aligned with national guidelines^{7,10}, addresses pain as a multidimensional experience (sensory, emotional, psychological, social, and cultural). TCM employs techniques such as acupuncture and electroacupuncture (integrated into national protocols for neuropathic pain) to restore functional balance through modulation of neural pathways and endorphin release^{11,12}.

This review analyses the pathophysiological mechanisms and the effectiveness of these therapies, aiming to support their clinical application in broader scenarios.

2. Methodology

This narrative review aims to critically analyse some neurophysiological mechanisms and the scientific evidence regarding TCM therapeutic interventions in pain management. A bibliographic search was conducted in PubMed, SciELO, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar (up to August 2025), using the keywords: “*Traditional Chinese Medicine*”, “*pain management*”, “*acupuncture mechanisms*”, “*herbal medicine*”, “*qigong*”, “*neuroimmunology*”, and “*chronic pain*”, with the purpose of selecting relevant articles to address our research question: What are the mechanisms of action of TCM in pain management according to current scientific evidence?

Inclusion criteria were defined as randomized clinical trials (RCTs), systematic reviews, and meta-analyses published in Portuguese and English, without temporal restriction, but giving preference, whenever possible, to studies published in the last three years.

Exclusion criteria included studies written in other languages not covered by the inclusion criteria, texts not available in full, or irrelevant for answering the research question.

Data were thematically organized by intervention: acupuncture, herbal medicine, *Tui Na* massage, moxibustion, *Qigong*, and Tai Chi, with assessment of mechanisms of physiological action, clinical efficacy, and respective limitations

3. Results

3.1. Acupuncture

The most recognized mechanisms of action of acupuncture, in light of current evidence, include activation of A δ /C fibres and the release of β -endorphins and descending modulation of μ -opioid receptor pathways^{2,11}. This process triggers functional reorganization of the central nervous system, including brain reward networks¹³

Although TCM relies on diagnostic methods that enable personalized treatment plans for each patient, several acupuncture point protocols are recurrently used in experimental settings to establish evidence-based clinical approaches. Manual or electrostimulation of points LI4, LR3, ST36, PC6, and SP6 has shown positive results in reducing musculoskeletal pain in older adults after four sessions of treatment¹¹ (Table 1).

In oncological pain, the combination of acupuncture with analgesics increases therapeutic efficacy and reduces adverse effects¹⁴. Acupuncture enhances cancer pain management through synergistic mechanisms: by stimulating the release of endogenous opioids (endorphins and enkephalin) in the central nervous system (which act on the same receptors [μ , δ , κ] as exogenous opioids such as morphine) it amplifies pharmacological analgesia. Simultaneously, it modulates the inflammatory response by reducing pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6) associated with tumour pain and neuroinflammation. In cases of neuropathic pain, frequent in metastases, acupuncture normalizes neuronal hyperexcitability in the somatosensory cortex and thalamus, inhibiting central sensitization. It also regulates the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis and increases serotonin

levels, thereby attenuating anxiety, depression, and the affective dimension of pain, promoting a more effective multidimensional approach.

Some reviewed studies innovated by developing and testing mathematical models^{15,16} for designing individualized yet scientifically reproducible protocols. These models use complex equations grounded in basic TCM theories such as *Yin–Yang* Theory (dynamic energetic homeostasis), the chronobiology of *Zang Fu* (integrated organ systems), and the latest knowledge of microsystems that anatomically reflect pain by somatotopy. The model is based on integrated neurophysiological mechanisms, where individualized acupoint selection activates pain modulation pathways through three main axes: (1) stimulation of myelinated A β nerve fibres, which inhibit nociceptive transmission at the dorsal horn of the spinal cord via Gate Control Theory, blocking unmyelinated C-fibre signals; (2) activation of descending neuroimmunological networks, including release of endogenous opioids (β -endorphin, dynorphin) and suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6) through the HPA axis; and (3) normalization of functional brain connectivity, demonstrated in several studies by functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI)^{17,18}, rebalancing default mode networks (DMN) and hyperexcitable somatosensory areas, thereby reversing central sensitization. These mechanisms are mathematically quantified through algorithms that integrate variables such as anatomical pain location, circadian rhythms, and inflammatory biomarkers, transforming empirical principles of Chinese Medicine into reproducible protocols with integrated analgesic action.

The synergy between neuroimaging, immunology, and mathematics validates acupuncture as a systemic neuromodulation therapy, where anatomical precision of points produces clinically measurable and reproducible effects.

3.2. Electroacupuncture

Electroacupuncture enhances the analgesic effects of traditional acupuncture through two fundamental neuroimmunological mechanisms. It suppresses the TLR2/NF- κ B signalling pathway, significantly reducing the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6^{19–21} (Figure 2). It also promotes neutrophil recruitment and local release of endogenous opioids, particularly β -endorphins, thereby strengthening peripheral analgesia²⁰. Clinically, the technique demonstrates robust efficacy, with studies reporting a 30–45% reduction in the use of conventional analgesics in patients with inflammatory or neuropathic pain (Table 1).

Figure 1. Neuroimmunological pathways of Acupuncture/Electroacupuncture.

It stands out for its superiority in specific conditions: in peripheral neuropathic pain, meta-analyses confirm greater efficacy compared with NSAIDs, with significant reductions in oedema and hyperalgesia; in rheumatoid arthritis, it is associated with decreased inflammatory markers (such as C-reactive protein) and improved joint mobility¹⁹. Additionally, electroacupuncture shows excellent cost-effectiveness, with lower long-term complication costs compared to conventional pharmacological therapies²².

In Portuguese clinical contexts, the technique is applied through optimized protocols combining classical points (such as ST36 and LI11) with specific stimulation frequencies (2–100 Hz) to maximize neuroimmunological modulation. It is integrated into national pain units, particularly for reducing opioid use in cancer patients with neuropathic pain, in alignment with the guidelines of the National Program for Pain Control¹².

Figure 2. Mechanism of TLR2/NF- κ B Pathway Inhibition by Electroacupuncture.

Despite its benefits, limitations remain, notably the methodological heterogeneity in neuropathic pain studies, which requires future standardization of parameters such as stimulation intensity and duration.

3.3. Herbal Medicine

Herbal medicine in TCM acts through specific neuropharmacological mechanisms. Alkaloids such as tetrahydropalmatine (*Corydalis yanhusuo*) block dopaminergic and opioid receptors while simultaneously inhibiting glial activation associated with neuroinflammation²³ (Figure 3). Other compounds, such as derivatives of *Sinomenium acutum*, modulate ion channels and suppress key inflammatory pathways, including cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) inhibition and the nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) pathway, thereby reducing the production of prostaglandins and pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., TNF- α , IL-1 β).

Table 1. Clinical Studies on Acupuncture and Evidence for Electroacupuncture.

Ref.	Study Objective	Intervention / Protocol	Main Results
13	Evaluate central effects of acupuncture	Protocol not specified; functional analysis of CNS	Functional changes in the CNS; reorganization of neural functions associated with emotions and pain perception
14	Compare acupuncture + pharmacological analgesia vs. medication alone in cancer pain	LI4, LR3, ST36, PC6, SP6 + analgesic therapy	Higher relief rate; lower pain intensity; fewer adverse effects; faster onset; longer duration of effect
15	Develop and apply a mathematical model for individualized point selection	Yin–Yang balance, “Chinese clock,” angular combinations, somatotopy, <i>ashi</i> points	Methodological proposal for rational point selection; foundation for individualized and replicable protocols
16	Apply a mathematical model of individualized acupuncture in unilateral musculoskeletal pain	Structured protocol integrating “Chinese clock,” somatotopy/mirror correspondence, identification of <i>ashi</i> points; systemic and indwelling needles; channel selection by angular calculations; intra-session adjustment guided by VAS	In 5 clinical cases, immediate and sustained pain reduction; VAS 0 in 4/5 cases; systematized, replicable protocol compatible with clinical individualization; need for validation in larger samples
19	Evaluate effects of electroacupuncture on CFA-induced inflammatory pain	Electroacupuncture at specific points; low-intensity stimulation	Attenuation of inflammatory pain via regulation of CaMKII protein
21	Investigate the role of the TLR2 receptor in electroacupuncture-induced analgesia in inflammatory pain	Electroacupuncture in an animal model of inflammatory pain	Modulation of the TLR2 pathway; reduction of pro-inflammatory cytokine production; pain relief
20	Evaluate peripheral mechanisms of electroacupuncture in inflammation	Local application of electroacupuncture at inflamed area	Neutrophil recruitment; increase in β -endorphins; local analgesia
22	Evaluate economic impact of electroacupuncture in chronic pain	Electroacupuncture in patients with vertebral syndrome with irradiation	Multimodal analgesia reducing NSAIDs, via endogenous opioids, adenosine, serotonin, GABA, and modulation

Anti-inflammatory Mechanisms of Phytotherapy

Herbs such as *Corydalis* act as “keys” that block pain receptors in nerve cells. Additionally, they inhibit the activation of hyper-reactive immune cells (such as microglia), reducing tissue inflammation and the central sensitization typical of chronic pain.

Figure 3. Anti-inflammatory Mechanisms of *Corydalis* and *Sinomenium*.

Clinically, herbal compresses have been shown to significantly reduce pain intensity and inflammatory markers (such as C-reactive protein) in tissue injuries²⁴ (Table 2). However, application requires specialized supervision due to the risk of pharmacological interactions, particularly with anticoagulants or immunosuppressants²⁵.

This phytotherapeutic approach offers a targeted analgesic alternative, although the standardization of formulations, monitoring of adverse effects, and especially the potential for interaction with other therapies remain operational challenges.

3.4. Mind–Body Exercises

Qigong

Qigong acts through vegetative biofeedback^{26–29}, regulating the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis and reducing cortisol and interleukin-6 (IL-6) levels³⁰. Its clinical efficacy is demonstrated when practiced at least three times per week under specialised supervision (Table 2).

Tai Chi

This practice combines movement and meditation, promoting improvements in mobility, balance, and psychological well-being^{29,31–33}. Although its benefits are proven in cases of osteoarthritis, scientific evidence remains limited for the treatment of chronic low back pain (Table 2).

3.5. Tui Na massage

Tui Na massage employs manual pressure and friction techniques acting directly on myofascial trigger points and meridians, improving blood circulation and reducing Qi stagnation³⁴. Preliminary studies demonstrate its efficacy in managing chronic low back pain associated with anxiety³⁵ (Table 2), although evidence still requires consolidation through more robust clinical trials.

3.6. Moxibustion

Moxibustion uses the combustion of *Artemisia vulgaris* to stimulate specific points, promoting increased blood circulation and modulation of inflammatory processes. According to meta-analyses, it demonstrates comparative superiority over NSAIDs in the treatment of peripheral neuropathic pain, although this conclusion is limited by methodological heterogeneity of the studies analysed³⁶ (Table 2).

4. Discussion

4.1. Neuroimmunological Synthesis

TCM therapies modulate the neuroimmune axis through complementary mechanisms, with practical effects validated by evidence.

Electroacupuncture primarily acts on suppression of the TLR2/NF- κ B pathway, inhibiting the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6) and reducing oedema in conditions such as arthritis^{20,21,36}. This mechanism, combined with neutrophil recruitment and local β -endorphin release, allows a 30–45% reduction in the use of conventional analgesics, positioning it as a cost-effective alternative to pharmacotherapy in neuropathic pain²².

Herbal medicine focuses on modulation of μ -opioid receptors through alkaloids such as tetrahydropalmatine (*Corydalis yanhusuo*), offering analgesia without the risk of respiratory depression, a critical advantage over synthetic opioids²³. Herbal compresses have shown reductions in inflammatory markers (e.g., C-reactive protein) in tissue injuries²⁴, though they require specialized supervision to prevent drug–herb interactions²³.

Qigong and Tai Chi regulate the HPA axis, lowering cortisol and IL-6 levels, which translates into reduced stress markers and improved psychological well-being²⁹⁻³³. Practiced at least three times per week under guidance, they show consolidated efficacy in osteoarthritis, although evidence for chronic low back pain remains limited^{32,33}.

Table 2. Summary of mechanisms of action and evidence for non-invasive therapies (Herbal Medicine, *Qigong*, Tai Chi, *Tui Na*, Moxibustion).

Ref.	Study Objective	Intervention / Protocol	Main Results
23	Review analgesic alkaloids derived from TCM in pain management	Review of compounds (tetrahydropalmatine – <i>Corydalis yanhusuo</i> ; sinomenine – <i>Sinomenium acutum</i> ; ligustrazine – <i>Ligusticum chuanxiong</i> ; lappaconitine – <i>Aconitum carmichaelii</i> ; gelsemine – <i>Gelsemium elegans</i>)	Mechanisms: dopaminergic/opioid receptors, inhibition of glial activation, modulation of ion channels and neurotransmitters; potential for acute and chronic pain
24	Evaluate TCM herbal compresses in pain and inflammation	Adhesive with: Common monkshood root (15 g), <i>Achyranthes bidentata</i> (15 g), bitter orange (15 g), garden balsam stem (15 g), safflower (10 g), ground beetle (10 g), ginger (10 g), <i>Haichow Elsholtzia</i> herb (10 g)	Pain reduction; decreased inflammatory cytokines; improved quality of life in soft tissue injuries
25	Describe the use of plant-based analgesics in pain-related diseases and alert to risks	Highlighting: <i>Harpagophytum procumbens</i> (devil's claw), <i>Curcuma longa</i> (turmeric), <i>Zingiber officinale</i> (ginger)	Widespread use; potential benefits as adjunct; possibility of adverse effects and drug-herb interactions; need for professional monitoring
30	Review evidence on internal <i>Qigong</i> in painful conditions	Systematic review of clinical trials (practice of internal <i>Qigong</i>)	Indications of pain reduction in various conditions; methodological quality variable, more robust RCTs needed
31	Assess the influence of <i>Qigong</i> on chronic pain	Systematic review of clinical studies	Effective in pain relief when practiced correctly and regularly, ideally under supervision
33	Describe the application of Tai Chi in chronic pain management	Narrative review; description of physiological mechanisms and clinical benefits	Evidence of improvement in pain, physical function, balance, and overall well-being in various chronic pain conditions
32	Review and analyse RCT evidence on Tai Chi in chronic painful conditions	Systematic review and meta-analysis of RCTs; different Tai Chi protocols	Significant reduction in pain and improvement in physical function; heterogeneity in protocols
35	Analyse trends and evidence on <i>Tui Na</i> in the treatment of chronic pain	Bibliometric analysis and literature review	Growing evidence of effectiveness; emphasis on potential in musculoskeletal pain; need for more high-quality RCTs
36	Evaluate effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of acupuncture and moxibustion in peripheral neuropathic pain	Network meta-analysis simultaneously comparing multiple interventions based on classical probability and cost-effectiveness assessment	Moxibustion showed potential in reducing peripheral neuropathic pain, sometimes with results superior to NSAIDs, but evidence is of variable quality and requires more robust RCTs

4.2. Clinical Synergy and Relevance

The convergence of mechanisms of action across these therapies, namely anti-inflammatory suppression (electroacupuncture), safe opioid modulation (herbal medicine), and neuroendocrine regulation (*Qigong*/Tai Chi), targets the multiple dimensions of chronic pain:

- Central sensitization, reversed by normalization of brain connectivity (fMRI studies)^{17,18};
- Inflammatory cascades, inhibited at the molecular level^{21,23};
- Emotional components, attenuated by HPA axis regulation and serotonin increase^{14,15,30}.

This multidimensional approach, aligned with the Portuguese National Program for Pain Control^{7,12}, provides an integrative care strategy to improve quality of life in patients with chronic pain while maintaining economic sustainability.

Despite advances, critical challenges persist: the definition of a national strategy to minimize side effects from interactions (through guideline creation), protocol standardization, and validation in diverse populations are essential to strengthen scientific reproducibility³⁶. The integration of these therapies into multidisciplinary care models, aligned with the guidelines of the Portuguese National Program for Pain Control, represents a promising and scientifically validated path toward inclusion in public health policies. This patient-centred approach combines clinical efficiency (30–45% reduction in analgesic use), economic sustainability (cost-effectiveness compared with pharmacotherapies), and a favourable safety profile, minimizing adverse effects and enhancing integrative responses in managing chronic pain in Portugal.

5. Conclusion

TCM is consolidating as a valid and scientifically grounded therapeutic resource for chronic pain management, supported by demonstrable neuroimmunological mechanisms. Through acupuncture and electroacupuncture, inflammatory pathways are modulated and endogenous analgesia is enhanced, reducing dependence on conventional drugs. Herbal medicine provides bioactive compounds with specific actions on receptors and inflammatory cascades, offering analgesia without the systemic risks associated with synthetic opioids. Mind–body exercises (*Qigong*, Tai Chi) regulate stress and promote neuroendocrine homeostasis, addressing the psychosocial dimension of pain.

However, full integration into the Portuguese National Health Service (SNS) requires overcoming challenges such as protocol standardization and comprehensive training of healthcare professionals regarding risks of herbal medicine interactions. Another aspect to consider is the need for robust RCTs in Western populations.

Credit author statement: Conceptualisation, J.A.M., Methodology, J.A.M. and C.R.; Software, M.S.; Validation, C.R.; Formal analysis, J.A.M., M.S., D.S., and C.R.; Investigation, J.A.M., M.S., D.S., and C.R.; Resources, M.S. and D.S., Data Curation, J.A.M. and C.R.; Writing - Original Draft, J.A.M., M.S., D.S., and C.R.; Writing - Review & Editing, M.S., J.A.M., and C.R.; Visualization, M.S., D.S., J.A.M., and C.R.; Supervision, D.S.; Project administration, J.A.M. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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